

Archive of Oncology publishes original articles describing clinical research on the cellular and molecular characterization, prevention, diagnosis, and therapy of human cancer. All submissions undergo peer review.

Founder, owner and publisher: Oncology Institute of Vojvodina, Institutski put 4, 21204 Sremska Kamenica, Serbia

By the decision No. FI 81/07 issued by the Chamber of Commerce, Novi Sad, dated April 30, 2007, *Institute of Oncology Sremska Kamenica* was registered under the new name *Oncology Institute of Vojvodina*.

Archive of Oncology is covered by **Biomedicina Serbica, Biomedicina Vojvodina, Biomedicina Oncologica, EMBASE/Excerpta Medica, ExtraMED, SCOPUS.**

UDC 616-006
ISSN 0354-8139

DOI is assigned by Narodna biblioteka Srbije, Skerlićeva 1, 11000 Belgrade

Preparation for printing and printing:
Printing firm „Stojkov Štamparija d.o.o.“
Stojkov Mihajlo, Laze Nančića 34-36, Novi Sad, Serbia

Circulation: 100

Novi Sad, 2012

Editorial office:
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Archive of Oncology is financed by the Oncology Institute of Vojvodina and partly by the Ministry of Science and Environmental Protection of the Republic of Serbia. The journal is registered by the Bureau for Intellectual Property of Serbia.

Archive of Oncology is published four times a year, in April, July, October and December.
Publication program in 2012: Volume 20 (four issues).

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2012 subscription rates, Volume 20*
Serbia: Individuals: Din. 3 240; Institutions: Din. 4 320
Europe: Individuals: EUR 40; Institutions: EUR 50
Elsewhere: Individuals: US\$ 70; Institutions: US\$ 100

* Before subscribing for the journal please contact the Editorial Office for getting an invoice.

CIP – Каталогизacija y publikaciji
Библиотека Матице српске, Нови Сад

616-006

ARCHIVE of Oncology / Supplement / editor in chief
Vladimir Baltić. – Vol. 3, br. 1 (nov. 1995)–. –
Sremska Kamenica: Institute of Oncology, 1995–. – 28 cm

Povremeno
ISSN 0354-8139

COBISS.SR-ID 45273858

ISSN 0354-8139

UDC 616-006

ARCHIVE OF ONCOLOGY

Founded 1993

Editor-in-Chief: Vladimir Baltić

Vol 20 Suppl 1
April 2012

<http://www.onk.ns.ac.rs/Archive>

Official Journal of the
ONCOLOGY INSTITUTE OF VOJVODINA
SREMSKA KAMENICA
SERBIA

UDC: 616-006:616-072:2-455:616.8-009.7

Contribution of nuclear medical diagnostic procedures in establishing the causes of bone pain in children

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Determining the cause of bone pain in children can be problematic. Various conditions can cause these symptoms: fractures, myositis, osteomyelitis, septic arthritis, disorders of blood supply to the hip and other benign causes, but it can also be the first sign of a serious systemic disease or certain type of tumors and malignant cancers. In November 2009, a 5-year-old male child with sudden onset of left knee pain and limping over the last 30 days was admitted to the hospital with impression of existing benign tumor in the left leg. He did not have any history of trauma. He did not suffer from any major medical problems and there was no family history of skeletal problems. C-reactive protein, full blood count and erythrocyte sedimentation rate were normal. X-ray of his left leg showed periosteal reaction of the upper part of diaphysis of left femur with thickening of the cortex. The bone scan using 375 MBq 99mTc-DPD revealed increased uptake of tracer in upper and medium part of diaphysis of the left femur and small focal uptake in thoracic spine (processus spinosus VTh3). The left leg MRI showed osteolytic lesion of left femur, and small nodular changes in thoracic spine (processus spinosus VTh3). Bone biopsy of the left femur showed active nonspecific purulent inflammation. These data suggest that a bone scan using 99mTc-labeled phosphate should be an important part of diagnostic panel in examination of bone pain in pediatric cases. Bone scan can be useful in differential diagnosis of cortical reaction in various pathological conditions in pediatric cases.

Key words: Pain; Bone and Bones; Diagnostic Imaging; Pediatrics; Technetium Tc 99m Pyrophosphate; Nuclear Medicine

UDC: 616.61-006:615-085

Assessment of kidney function prior to peptide receptor radionuclide therapy

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Peptide receptor radiation therapy (PRRT) with radiolabeled octreotide analogs is effective in patients with somatostatin receptor-positive tumors, most notably in neuroendocrine tumors. The kidney appears to be the critical organ during radionuclide therapy because of peptide reabsorption and retention in the proximal tubules after glomerular filtration. We presented results of kidney functions tests that were used for patients who had undergone PRRT for neuroendocrine tumors with 90Y-DOTATOC with special reference to the pathophysiology of preexisting multiple risk factors for kidney impairment. We conducted several methods routinely used in clinical practice to determine kidney function (serum creatinine, serum cystatin C, creatinine clearance (CrCl) through 24-h urine collection and mathematical equations – 'modification of a diet in renal disease' equation – MDRD and Cockcroft-Gault). A very accurate measurement of individual kidney function (glomerular filtration rate (GFR) and effective renal plasma flow) was performed by 99Tc-diethylene triamine penta-acetic acid and 131I-orthoiodohippurate plasma clearance. Patients' age, preexisting kidney diseases, and chronic comorbidities contribute to the risk of renal impairment. Based on the fact that clinically relevant differences have been assessed between calculated values and the real situation, mathematical calculation of GFR or CrCl does not seem to be appropriate to assess individual renal function precisely enough.

Key words: Kidney Function Tests; Neuroendocrine Tumors; Radiopharmaceuticals; Receptors, Peptide; Glomerular Filtration Rate; Renal Plasma Flow; Technetium Tc 99m Pentetate; Iodohippuric Acid

UDC: 616.61:616.12-008.331.1:616-072

Value of the renal vascular resistance index in patients with essential hypertension

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High blood pressure is one of the leading causes of kidney failure. Early detection of changes in kidney function in patients with essential hypertension can prevent consecutive renal failure. The Doppler resistive index (RI) ($(\text{peak systolic velocity} - \text{end diastolic velocity}) / \text{peak systolic velocity}$) was advanced as a useful parameter for quantifying the alterations in renal blood flow that may occur with a kidney disease. The aim of the study was to measure the renal vascular resistance in patients with essential hypertension and to correlate RI with kidney functional tests by measuring glomerular filtrate rate (GFR) with DTPA clearance. The study included 60 patients with essential hypertension and 30 age-matched normotensive control examinees. The renal vascular resistance index (RI) was determined by use of Doppler ultrasound. GFR was determined by DTPA clearance in blood samples taken at 120 and 180 minutes. There was a statistically significant difference between the RI values in hypertensive and normotensive patients (mean RI in hypertensive patients was 0.67 ± 0.06 and in healthy controls 0.58 ± 0.04). RI correlated significantly with DTPA clearance ($r = -0.58, p = 0.001$). RI also correlated with patients' age and duration of hypertension but did not correlate with systolic and diastolic blood pressure and creatinine clearance. The increased renal vascular resistance in hypertensive patients could be a sign of changes in kidney function, which is why the renal vascular resistance index can be an important noninvasive parameter in the follow-up of patients with essential hypertension.

Key words: Hypertension; Vascular Resistance; Kidney Function Tests; Glomerular Filtration Rate; Ultrasonography, Doppler; Technetium Tc 99m Pentetate

UDC: 616.61:616.12-008.331.1

Renal haemodynamic in overweight hypertension women

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Overweight and obesity have become mass phenomena with a pronounced upward trend in prevalence in most countries throughout the world. The existence of a direct relationship between body mass and arterial pressure is well recognized. However, the effect of overweight on known target organs of hypertension is not clearly understood. We undertook the present studies to assess renal haemodynamic in overweight subjects, measuring effective renal plasma flow (ERPF) by clearances of ^{131}I -orthoiodohippurate. The study was conducted in 64 women (32 overweight, mean age 43.13 ± 12.9 and 32 normal weight, mean age 52.69 ± 11.9 respectively) who were with untreated, uncomplicated essential hypertension and normal values of kidney function test. Mean body mass index in the group of normal weight women was 22.09 kg/m^2 and 28.87 kg/m^2 in the overweight group ($p < 0.05$). Lean body mass (LBM) was 47.72 kg and 55.19 kg in overweight women. The average systolic and diastolic blood pressure in overweight women was $150 \pm 15 \text{ mm}$ and $110 \pm 18 \text{ mm Hg}$ and in women of normal weight, it was 145 ± 12 and $111 \pm 12 \text{ mm Hg}$. Effective renal plasma flow (expressed as absolute values or values normalized for body surface area (BSA)) was decreased in overweighted when compared to lean subjects (512.8 vs. $553.18 \text{ ml/min/1.73m}^2, p < 0.05$). Clearance of ^{131}I -orthoiodohippurate normalized on LBM was similar in overweighted and normal weighted subjects (619.2 vs. $612.22 \text{ ml/min/1.73m}^2, p > 0.05$). In conclusion, our data showed that using ERPF/BSA criteria, the overweight persons would display inappropriately low values and would be misdiagnosed to have impaired renal perfusion. Therefore, we recommended using lean body mass, instead of body mass in formula for BSA to correct ERPF.

Key words: Overweight; Hypertension; Renal Plasma Flow, Effective; Iodine Radioisotopes; Iodohippuric Acid